

ATLAS Open Data: Discovering the Z and Higgs Bosons

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1 Overview

This lab exercise is designed to teach you about C++ and ROOT (a particle physics data analysis software) in the context of understanding the particle physics behind two fundamental particles. While these particles have already been discovered and thoroughly studied, it is extremely valuable to be introduced to the scientific method behind the search for these particles, namely the Z Boson and Higgs Boson. To do this, you will be working with ATLAS Open Data [1, 2].

Though C++ and ROOT certainly have a steep learning curve, this exercise will guide you through the more difficult sections and provide plenty of help and useful tips. You will notice that the code sections are very dense. While you should certainly read through them thoroughly, keep in mind they are only there to give you a working knowledge (and reference) to help you write code in later sections. Lastly, know that the data you will be working with is real data from the Large Hadron Collider (LHC)!

2 The Large Hadron Collider

The LHC is located in Geneva, Switzerland and is operated by the European Council for Nuclear Research, or CERN. Many governments provide some funding to CERN, who in turn uses those funds to advance research in high energy physics. So while you may think CERN is strictly a European organization, it is in fact a collaboration between many countries, with collection of physicists from hundreds of countries.

The LHC has a very simple method of initiating collisions. It accelerates bunches of 10^{11} protons to near light speeds then alters their path to have them collide with one another. Once this happens, the detectors in the LHC work quickly to decide what collision data to store and what to disregard.

The reason this is done is because it would be impossible to have enough storage to save the data of every single particle collision. Instead, physicists "tell" the detectors in the LHC to look for certain signals in collisions that might be worthwhile to analyze later, and so the detector stores these specific collisions. And after physicists have combed through this data and have discovered all there is to discover, some of the data is made available to the public, allowing exercises like this to be possible.

2.1 The Coordinate System of the LHC

Because of the structure of the LHC and nature of high energy collisions, a pseudorapidity coordinate system is used. Pseudorapidity, η , is defined as

$$\eta = -\ln\left[\tan\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right)\right], \quad (1)$$

with θ defined as the angle between the z axis (along direction of the beam) and the momentum vector. Another useful quantity we can define is the transverse momentum, p_{\perp} , which is invariant under frame transformations. This is also the plane in which the most of the collision products are deflected to. This is defined as

$$p_{\perp} = p \sin(\phi), \quad (2)$$

where ϕ is the angle between the x-axis and the momentum vector.

2.2 The ATLAS Detector

The ATLAS detector, which stands for A Toroidal LHC Apparatus, is one of the main detectors at the LHC. It was engineered to track particle interactions and movement, measure energy deposits with calorimeters, measure the momenta of muons, measure the luminosity (or how close together particles in the beams are), and quickly decided which events to store and which to discard (this is know as the trigger system). A model of ATLAS is show in Figure 1.

3 C++ Introduction

The goal of this section is to provide you with a basic understanding of coding in C++. Due to its nature, C++ can sometimes be tedious to work with, but with this section and help/examples in later sections, the code you will need to write should be clear with some careful thought.

3.1 Variable Types

In C++, unlike some other coding languages, the coder must assign every new variable they create a type. Other languages, like Python, do this automatically, but C++ needs to be explicitly told the variable type. The variable type is simply what sort of number a variable will hold. For the purposes of this lab exercise, you only need to know several variable types.

3.1.1 Integers (Int)

An integer type is simply a variable that holds a whole number, negative or positive. It is written as

```
1 int variable_name
```


Figure 1: A model showing the various parts of ATLAS [3]

3.1.2 Floats (float)

A float type is a variable that holds a number with decimal points, negative or positive. It is written as

```
1 float variable_name
```

3.1.3 Bool (bool)

A bool type is a variable that holds either a 0 or 1, and nothing else. It is often used to represent False and True, respectively. It is written as

```
1 bool variable_name
```

3.1.4 TLorentzVectors (TLorentzVector)

A TLorentzVector is a ROOT variable type. You will learn more about it later, but for now know this variable type simply stores the four TLorentzVector components of a given particle. It is written as

```
1 TLorentzVector variable_name
```

3.2 Pointers

In C++, a pointer variable points (or retrieves) the memory address of whatever variable the pointer is pointing at.

Syntax:

```
1 int variable1* variable2
```

The above can be read as variable1 is equal to the value of the integer pointed to by variable2.

3.3 For Loops

For loops are one of the most useful tools in coding. Simply put, a for loop will iterate (or go through every entry in a list), starting from a given position, ending at a given position, and iterating by a set factor. While iterating, the for loop will execute the provided code over each entry it loops over.

In C++, a for loop needs three arguments (or things within the parentheses). It needs a start argument (at which entry the for loop will start its iteration), a stop argument (at which entry the for loop will stop its iteration), and an iteration command (essentially telling the for loop what entry it should loop over next). This is useful for executing code over some sort of list with lots of data.

Syntax: The proper syntax for a for loop is as follows:

```
1 for (start; stop; iteration){}
```

Within a for loop, it is common to define a variable for the purposes of assigning a start, stop, and iteration. You will have to make sure to assign this variable an appropriate type (using the int type should suffice for this lab exercise). Look below for an example of a for loop with this variable.

```
1 for (int i = 0; i < some variable or number; ++i){}
```

This for loop will loop over a set of data, starting with the first, or zeroth, entry. It will then continue iterating as long as i, or the current entry, is less than some variable (which should have a defined value) or some value. This argument can look different depending on what you are wanting from the for loop. It could stop at the final entry, or it could stop once a given condition is met. The third argument, ++i, tells the for loop to move through each event by one's (if it starts at the first entry, it will then loop over the second, then third, fourth, etc.). The actual code for the loop would go in between the curly braces.

3.4 If Statements

If statements are another invaluable tool in coding. An if statement simply carries out a set of code if a given condition is met. In C++, an if statement only needs the condition which must be met as an argument. This is useful when you only want to do something specific to data entries that meet your set requirements. Also, if statements are commonly used within for loops.

Syntax: The proper syntax for an if statement is as follows:

```
1 if (condition is met){}
```

If statements are commonly used to skip over certain events that do not meet a condition or to only do something with events that do. For example, you could write code that skips over events that do not meet a certain condition. That would look like the following:

```
1 if (value < 10){continue;}
```

The above if statement skips over events that have a value less than 10. "continue;" is what tells the if statement to skip over those events.

Lastly, multiple if statements can be combined into one long if statement if you need to ensure an event meets several requirements. To do this, you will need to use "&&" to combine the different if statements. This looks like the following:

```
1 if (condition1 && condition2 && condition3){continue;}
```

The above if statement says that if conditions 1, 2, and 3 are met, then continue (skip) over the events that meet these conditions. Rather than having three separate if statements for the three conditions, they were neatly combined into one.

3.5 Cout Statements

Cout statements (read see out) are just lines of code that print out whatever you would like. This is a great way to check your code is working as you build it. You should be periodically coding in cout statements to check your code is retrieving the proper information from the data files.

Syntax: The proper syntax for a cout statement is as follows:

```
1 std::cout << "label of variable" << variable << std::endl;
```

In the above code, the text between the quotation marks is what will print out, and the variable between the angle brackets is the numerical value that will print out. Here is an example of printing out the number of particles in a given collision event.

```
1 std::cout << "Number of particles in this collision" <<  
2 particle_count << std::endl;
```

3.6 Macros

In C++, a macro is just a named piece of code that executes a certain task or tasks. Before a macro can be created, it must be voided. It should be noted that when labeling a macro, it is a good idea to label the file the macro is written in the same as the macro itself, as this allows ROOT to call on the macro properly.

Syntax: The proper syntax for voiding a macro is as follows:

```
1 void macro_name () {}
```

3.7 Arrays

In C++, and for the purposes of this exercise, arrays will simply be used as lists that store data. An array starts with the 0th position, and goes up by ones from there. A data value can not have a negative array position.

4 ROOT Introduction

In this section, you will learn the basics of using ROOT to access and analyze LHC data. While at first all the new information might seem overwhelming, keep in mind this section is only meant to be used as a reference when you start working on the Z boson and Higgs boson exercise. By no means should you attempt to fully memorize this information. Again, refer back to this section frequently to help you with writing your macros in the next sections. Also, if any properties or functions that are mentioned later do not appear in this section, you can always review the documentation for ROOT online.

4.1 Accessing ROOT

To open ROOT:

1. Open the terminal application
2. Load in the file in which the four data files are stored by typing "cd" followed by the file's location. Alternatively, you could type "cd" and drag and drop the file's icon into terminal.

3. Load in the four data files by typing "root DataFileName1.root DataFileName2.root etc." Make sure the data file's extension are ".root".
4. Terminal should output text that reads "Attaching file..." for each of the four data files.

4.2 TTrees

ROOT has a unique way of storing large amounts of data. In the data files you downloaded, the data is stored and organized into things called TTrees, which are a sort of array. Within each TTree, there are one or more branches, and within each branch there are many leafs. Each of the data files you downloaded has one branch, and each branch has numerous leafs.

So, in essence, a TTree is a top-down sort of organizational and structural array. You can access the names of a TTree's branches and leafs by opening something called a TBrowser

4.2.1 TBrowsers

To access a TBrowser, in terminal, type

```
1 new TBrowser
```

into terminal. Do this after you have loaded in the four data files and opened ROOT. This should bring up a new window with a drop-down window.

Opening a data file's drop-down view will reveal its branch name (ignore the 1 following the name), and opening the branches drop-down view will reveal its leafs. Double click on the leafs to look at different collections of data.

4.3 TChains

Now that you have learned what a TTree is, you will need to be familiar with another data organization concept in ROOT, the TChain. A TChain is simply multiple TTrees put together into one long chain. Say you link together 5 TTrees into one TChain, any macro you run on this TChain will run over all 4 of the TTrees at the same time, as if it was simply one giant data file.

4.3.1 Creating a TChain

Syntax: The proper syntax for creating a TChain is as follows:

```
1 TChain* chain = new TChain ("mini");
```

Code Breakdown: In the code above, we are defining a new TChain, which we are calling "chain". The asterisk above tells our code to define a storage spot in our computer that will store our TChain.

4.3.2 Adding Files to a TChain

So when we go to store data in our TChain, named "chain", we will use the function "AddFile()" on our TChain.

Syntax: The proper syntax for adding a data file to a TChain is as follows:

```
1 chain->AddFile("DataA.root");
```

Code Breakdown: Here, we are using the function "AddFile()" on our TChain to add our first data file. The arrow above is what allows us to use the function on the TChain, and whatever you choose to name the data files (make sure the names end with a ".root") goes in the quotation marks.

4.4 Histograms

4.4.1 What is a Histogram?

A histogram, as it will be used in the context of this lab exercise, is a plot that portrays the frequency of something happening, also known as a frequency distribution. On a histogram's x-axis, the different values of a given unit are shown for a given range. The x-axis is divided up into bins, which are just equal width intervals of the x-axis. The y-axis, then, shows how often a given value of the x-axis occurs, known as the occurrence frequency. Below is an example of a histogram.

Figure 2: Gaussian Distribution Histogram

As you can see in the above histogram, the x-axis has the number and the y-axis has the occurrence frequency. For example, the number 0 seems to have occurred roughly 250 times (out of the 10000 trials/entries), while the number 3 seems to have occurred about 5-10 times. You could make a histogram that has the weights of cars on the x-axis and how often each car weight occurs on the y-axis. Or a histogram with the die face number on the x-axis and the die face occurrence frequency on the y-axis.

4.4.2 Creating a TCanvas

ROOT requires you to create something called a TCanvas, which is essentially an empty window on your computer in which one or more histograms can be plotted on. Keep in mind that for a given macro, only one TCanvas is needed, regardless of how many histograms the macro will be creating.

Syntax: The proper syntax for creating a TCanvas and printing it is as follows:

```
1 TCanvas *c1 = new TCanvas ();
2 c1->Print();
```

Code Breakdown: In the above code, the new TCanvas is being called "c1".

4.4.3 Creating a Histogram

In ROOT, when creating a histogram, one must consider what type to assign to it, just as you assign types to variables. There are many different histogram types that serve various functions, but for the purposes of this lab exercise, you will only need to create a **TH1F** histogram type.

Syntax: The proper syntax for creating a new histogram is as follows:

```
1 TH1F *h1 = new TH1F ("box title", "plot title; x axis title; y axis
  title", number of bins, lower x boundary, upper x boundary);
```

Code Breakdown: In the above code, the histogram is being called h1. The strings (values between quotation marks) in the parentheses will act as labels on your histogram, with "box title" being the label for the statistics of the plot, and the others being labels for the entire plot, x axis, and y axis. Then, we have the number of bins our histogram will have and how far those bins stretch from on the x-axis.

4.4.4 Filling Histograms

Once a histogram has been created (and once you write the code that is able to calculate the desired variable(s)), you will need to fill your histogram with data.

Syntax: The proper syntax for filling a histogram with variable1 is as follows:

```
1 h1->Fill(variable1);
```

4.4.5 Drawing Histograms

Once a a histogram has been created and filled, and once a TCanvas has been created, you will be able to draw the histogram with a simple function.

Drawing a histogram with error bars can also be useful.

Syntax: The proper syntax for drawing a histogram with error bars is as follows:

```
1 h1->Draw("e"); // With error bars
2 h1-> Draw(); // Without error bars
```

4.4.6 Saving Histograms

You might find it useful to save a histogram as a pdf so you can refer back to it after termination your code. In ROOT, you can save a TCanvas, which will save all the histograms plotted on that TCanvas.

Syntax: The proper syntax to save a TCanvas as a pdf is as follows:

```
1 c1->Print("title.pdf");
```

Code Breakdown: Make sure to include the quotation marks.

4.4.7 Working with the TCanvas Window

Once you have successfully drawn a histogram, a new window titled "c1" should pop up somewhere on your computer screen. This is the TCanvas with the histogram. It is likely that for some histograms, the plot will not be zoomed in enough to see any true detail. Here is how to fix that.

1. Once the plot shows up, position your cursor right below the x-axis (not on the x-axis), preferably close to the zoomed out data
2. Click and drag your cursor towards the data that is zoomed out, dragging the highlighted box that appears past the origin
3. Stop once you have reach a zoom level with good detail
4. To unzoom, simply reposition your cursor right below the x-axis (not on the x-axis), then right click and select "unzoom"

5 Practice Example

5.1 The Example Problem

In this section we will be working through a short practice problem utilizing all or most of the C++ coding elements we have discussed so far, as well as some elements of ROOT. The problem we will be doing is making a macro that will create an array of random numbers, and then using a for loop, run through every entry and sort which entries are even and which are odd. We will then fill a histogram with the entries from the array and draw it. As this exercise is to help you gain a better understanding of C++ and Root before you begin the Z and Higgs Boson exercises, the final code will be provided at the end of this section.

5.2 Macro Section 1: Macro, TCanvas, and Histogram Creation

5.2.1 Beginning our Macro

To start, we need to create a file in any text editor. Give the file a relatively simple name that has the same name as the voided macro we will be creating. Also, you will need to include one package, "TRandom.h," that will allow us to generate random numbers in ROOT. So far, your code should look like this:

```
1 #include <TRandom.h>
2
3 void Example()
4 {
5
6 }
```

5.2.2 TCanvas, TRandom3, and Histogram

Our next step will be the creation of some important elements we will be needing. These are a TCanvas, a histogram, and a TRandom3 variable. Here is the script for creating the histogram and TCanvas:

```
1 TCanvas *c1 = new TCanvas();
2
3 TH1F *h1 = new TH1F("box title", "plot title;x axis title; y axis
   title", number of bins, lower x boundary, upper x boundary)
```

Code Breakdown: In the code above, we have created an empty histogram and the canvas that it will be drawn onto, h1 and c1 respectively, when we run the macro. You will want to change the boundaries and number of bins in the histogram depending on how you want your histogram to look. As a reminder, all of the code except for the inclusion of the package at the start should be *inside* the voided macro.

To finish off this section, try and create the TRandom3 variable the same way you created the variable c1 before.

5.2.3 Checkpoint

So far, your macro should look like this, with any blanks filled in:

```
1 #include <TRandom.h>
2
3 void Example()
4 {
5     TCanvas *c1 = new TCanvas();
6
7     TH1F *h1 = new TH1F("box title", "plot title;x axis title; y
8     axis title", number of bins, lower x boundary, upper x boundary
9     );
10
11     // Code for creating a TRandom3 variable
12 }
```

5.3 Macro Section 2: Array and For loop

5.3.1 Creating an Array

Next, we need to define an array of integers that we can fill with random numbers. Optionally, you can also define a variable for the total number of random integers you want to generate to make it easier to change later if you want. An example of the code for that looks like this:

```
1 int tot = 1000
2 int array[tot]
```

5.3.2 Creating the For Loop

This section will contain the rest of the code for this exercise, as there are only about 17 lines of code including lines for spacing. To begin, we need to create our for loop. Remember, a for loop has three arguments: (start;stop;iteration). Since we are looping over the entries of an array, and arrays start with the 0th entry, we will want to define a variable "i" that equals 0 for our starting argument. For our stop argument, we want the loop to finish on the final entry, so we can simply have the loop stop once our variable "i" is no longer less than the total numbers we have randomly generated. Finally, to iterate we simply just want to add 1 each time. This should all look like this once you are done:

```
1 for(int i = 0; i<tot; i++)
2 {
3
4 }
```

Now we need to start filling in our for loop. The first thing we want to do is start filling our array with random numbers. We can do this by using the "Uniform" function of our TRandom3 variable to randomly generate a uniform distribution of numbers between two variables. For this example I will be generating numbers between 1 and 10, but feel free to choose any range of numbers you want. Just don't forget to modify the x boundaries of your histogram to include this range of numbers. Note that I have named my TRandom3 variable "r3." The code should look like this:

```
1 for(int i = 0; i < tot; i++)
2 {
3     array[i] = r3->Uniform(1,11);
4
5 }
```

We now have a for loop that will fill an array with random numbers. We are not finished, however, as now we must sort these numbers by which ones are even and which are odd. To do this we will be using if and cout statements. First, we want to create if statements that will help us determine if the current entry in our array is even or odd. We can do this using the modulus operator in C++. The modulus operator divides the first argument by the second argument and then returns the remainder. Therefore, if we simply take the modulus of 2, we can determine if a number is even or odd depending on if it has a remainder or not, as all even numbers will return 0 and all odd numbers will return 1. After we make our if statement with its condition, we want to make a cout statements that will print out if the entry is even or odd. The code for the even numbers will be given, but try to fill in the odd if statement yourself.

```
1 for(int i = 0; i < tot; i++)
2 {
3     array[i] = r3->Uniform(1,11);
4
5     if(array[i] % 2 == 0)
6     {
7         std::cout<<array[i]<<" is even"<<std::endl;
8     }
9 }
```

Finally, to end our for loop and our macro, we want to fill our histogram with each entry of our array. Then, outside of our for loop, we will draw the histogram.

5.4 Conclusion

All together, your final code should look something like this:

```

1 #include <TRandom.h>
2
3 void Example()
4 {
5     TCanvas *c1 = new TCanvas();
6
7     TH1F *h1 = new TH1F("box title","plot title;x axis label; y
8     axis label", 100, 0, 11);
9
10    TRandom3 *r3 = new TRandom3();
11
12    int tot = 1000;
13
14    int array[tot];
15
16    for(int i=0; i<tot; i++)
17    {
18        array[i] = r3->Uniform(1,11)
19
20        if(array[i] % 2 == 0)
21        {
22            std::cout<<array[i]<<" is even"<<std::endl;
23        }
24
25        if(array[i] % 2 == 1)
26        {
27            std::cout<<array[i]<<" is odd"<<std::endl;
28        }
29
30        h1->Fill(array[i]);
31    }
32
33    h1->Draw();
34 }

```

Notes: As was stated before, for this example we generated numbers between 1 and 10, and generated 1000 random numbers. You may have generated a different amount in a different range, which is fine. Also, we made the amount of bins equal to 100 so that we can see clearly the spikes at each number.

Your final histogram you draw should look something like this:

Figure 3: Final Histogram

6 Physics Context

6.1 The Standard Model

The Standard Model is the leading theoretical framework that describes the fundamental particles and their interactions. It has repeatedly been held up through various experiments. In it, there are three main types of particles: leptons, quarks, and bosons.

Leptons are particles like the electron, and its cousins, the tau and muon. Bosons are particles like the photon, Z, and Higgs bosons. These particles are the force-carrying particles. They mediate forces like the electromagnetic force (the photon) and weak nuclear force (the W and Z bosons).

Figure 4: Standard Model of Elementary Particles [4]

6.2 Decay Modes

Decay modes in particle physics is when a particle decays into one or more other particles. Many particles do this, including the Z and Higgs bosons. The Z boson will often decay into two leptons, and physicists often look for these two leptons in collisions then back track to a Z boson. The Higgs boson will often decay into two Z bosons, which in turn decay into two leptons each (a total of four leptons). The leptons that the Z boson decay into have certain requirements that they must uphold; they must both have the same flavor, e.g. two muons or two electrons, and they must have opposite charges.

Figure 5: Higgs Boson decay into four charged leptons

In figure 4 above, we can see one of the decay modes of the Higgs Boson. We see the top quarks collide into a Higgs Boson, which then decays into a Z and virtual Z Boson (explained in next section) which then each decay into two matching leptons.

The reason physicists don't try to directly observe the bosons is because once a boson is created in a collision, it often decays incredibly fast. For example, the Higgs has a life time of roughly 10^{-22} seconds [5].

6.3 The Vacuum

Now, if you look up the masses of the Z and Higgs bosons, you may notice that adding up two Z bosons will result in a mass much higher than that of a Higgs boson. But how can that be? The answer lies in the uncertainty principle.

When a Higgs boson decays, it decays into one on-shell Z boson and one off-shell Z boson. These terms signify if a Z boson has its normal mass of 91 GeV, with on-shell indicating it does. An off-shell, or virtual, Z boson will have as much mass as is needed to make up the difference between the Higgs boson mass and the on-shell Z boson mass. This is roughly 34 GeV. But if a particle has a mass of 34 GeV, how can it be a Z boson?

This virtual Z boson will borrow the remaining energy/mass it needs from the vacuum to make-up this energy/mass. This energy/mass will then be returned to the vacuum very quickly. This process follows the equation

$$\Delta E \cdot \Delta t \geq \frac{\hbar}{2} \tag{3}$$

In this formula, as the energy borrowed increases, the duration of the time decreases. So when this virtual Z boson borrows the energy it needs to be a Z boson, it can only do so for a short amount of time. And once the Z boson decay to two leptons, this energy is then returned to the vacuum.

7 Z Boson Exercise

7.1 A Quick Overview

In this exercise, you will be using some of the your newly learned ROOT and physics knowledge to create a macro that will create a histogram that provides evidence for the Z boson's existence. We will work through sections of the code at a time, making sure to understand what the code is doing and what physics underlies the code. These sections are:

- Macro, TChain, and Histogram Creation
- Loading the Data into the Macro
- Identifying the Leading and Subleading Leptons
- Creating a Dilepton System
- Filling the Histogram
- Flavor, charge, and Tight ID Requirements

Keep in mind, parts of the macro in this exercise and the next will be provided to you as understanding what certain lines of code do is not important for the purposes of these exercises. To get started, download the data from <https://opendata.cern.ch/record/15003>.

7.2 Macro Section 1: Macro, TChain, and Histogram Creation

7.2.1 First Items

To begin our macro, we will need to create a file in your choice of a text editor. Whatever you choose, give the file a simple name and create a voided macro with the same name as the file. We will also need to include several packages that allow us to carry out certain actions. So far, your macro should look like the following:

```
1 #include <vector>
2 #include <iostream>
3 #include "TChain.h"
4 #include "TLorentzVector.h"
5
6 void ZBoson() {}
```

7.2.2 TChain

Next we will want to create our TChain, which, as previously explained, allows us to combine multiple TTrees into one chain of TTrees. In our exercise, we will want to combine all four data files into one chain. The script to do this is as follows:

```
1 TChain* chain = new TChain ("mini");
```

Code Breakdown: In the code above, we are defining a new TChain, which we are calling "chain". The asterisk above tells our code to define a storage spot in our computer that will store our TChain.

So when we go to store data in our TChain, named "chain", we will use the function "AddFile()" on our TChain. Here is how we would add our first data file:

```
1 chain->AddFile("DataA.root");
```

Code Breakdown: Here, we are using the function "AddFile()" on our TChain to add our first data file. The arrow above is what allows us to use the function on the TChain, and whatever you choose to name the data files (make sure the names end with a ".root") goes in the quotation marks.

Tasks: Write script to add the three other files to the TChain.

7.2.3 Creating Data Pointers

We will need to write code that creates variables to store the values of the coordinates of the particles, $(p_{\perp}, \eta, \phi, E)$. For the first data file, the code is as follows:

```
1 vector<float>* lep_pt = new vector<float>;
```

Code Breakdown: This line of code creates a new vector, which is a float, that will store the values of lep_pt. It can be read as "The vector equals the value of the float pointed to by lep_pt."

Tasks: Create new vectors for the other three variables.

7.2.4 Storing the Data

Now that we have created vectors to store the data from the TTrees, we will need to write script that makes the macro "grab" the data from these TTrees and stores it in one of the vectors. The following is an example of how to do this with the lep_pt vector.

```
1 chain->SetBranchAddresses("lep_pt", & lep_pt);
```

Code Breakdown: This line of code tells our TChain that the data that will be stored in the vector lep_pt will be found at the branch address (within the TTree) with the name "lep_pt". If you are unsure whether your variables and the branch address have the same name, you can utilize a TBrowser to view the branch address for each variable.

Tasks: Write script to tell the TChain where to find a vector's values and where to store these values for the three other variables.

7.2.5 Creating a Histogram

For the last part of this section, we will need to set up a histogram so that we can later fill it with data. To do this, we must first create a canvas on which the histogram will be drawn. Once this is done, we can create the histogram. Make sure to pay attention to this code as it will be useful in the next exercise.

```
1 TCanvas *c1 = new TCanvas();
2
3 TH1F *h1 = new TH1F ("box title", "plot title; x axis title; y axis
4   title",
5   number of bins, lower x boundary, upper x boundary);
```

Code Breakdown: The first line of code above creates a new canvas, on which the histogram will be drawn. The next two lines of code create a new histogram titled "h1", and sets the title, bin number, and the domain of the plot.

7.2.6 Checkpoint

So far, your macro should look similar to this, with the blanks filled in.

```
1 #include <vector>
2 #include <iostream>
3 #include "TChain.h"
4 #include "TLorentzVector.h"
5
6 void ZBoson() {
7
8   // Creating a TChain
9   TChain* chain = new TChain ("mini");
10
11  // Adding files to the TChain
12  chain->AddFile("DataA.root");
13  // Code for second file
14  // Code for third file
15  // Code for fourth file
16
17  // Creating Data Pointers
18  vector<float>* lep_pt = new vector<float>;
19  // Code for second vector/coordinate
20  // Code for third vector/coordinate
21  // Code for fourth vector/coordinate
22
23  // Storing the Data
24  chain->SetBranchAddress("lep_pt", & lep_pt);
25  // Code for storing the second variable
26  // Code for storing the third variable
27  // Code for storing the fourth variable
28
29  //Creating a Histogram
30  TCanvas *c1 = new TCanvas();
31
32  TH1F *h1 = new TH1F ("box title", "plot title; x axis title; y axis
33    title",
34    number of bins, lower x boundary, upper x boundary);
35 }
```

7.3 Macro Section 2: Loading the Data into the Macro

7.3.1 Initiating a For Loop

Now that we have set up the macro, we will need to loop over all the events in the TChain to look for particle collision events that meet certain requirements. To do this, we will need to create a for loop that starts at the first event and ends at the final entry. Think back to the ROOT/C++ reading to help you. Keep in mind, you will need to define a "long" variable at the start of the for loop and assign it a value, such as:

```
1 for (long "variable" = "value", ... ){}
```

Code Breakdown: A function that may be useful is the "GetEntries();" function, which gets the entries from a TChain (as this function should be used on the TChain).

Tasks: Fill in the rest of the for loop.

7.3.2 Accessing the Data and Setting Requirements

Next, we will need to store the current entry (particle collision) we are on in the long variable previously defined. Then we will need to write script that allows the macro to know how many leptons are detected in the current event.

Code Breakdown: For the first part, you will need to use the "GetEntry();" function to store the current event in the long variable from the TChain. Next, you will need to define a new variable that will hold the number of leptons in each event. You will need to use the "size();" function on "lep_pt" to do so, which will require the use of the arrow operator. Store this number in a variable with a type that makes sense for the type of number being stored.

Next, we will need to set some sort of requirement so that we are not looking at events that we do not care about. Think about what we are looking for in the data. What does the Z boson decay into?

Code Breakdown: You will need to use an if statement and the command "continue;", which tells your code if some condition is not met, then skip the current event.

Tasks: Write script that:

- Stores current entry in the previously defined long variable
- Retrieves the number of leptons in the current event
- Sets a condition relating to events that we do not want our macro to look at

7.3.3 Array Positioning

Physics Context: As previously mentioned, the Z boson decays into two leptons. While none of the events the code is looking at should have less than two leptons, some may have more. Regardless of how many leptons are in an event, we will want to identify the highest p_{\perp} and second highest p_{\perp} leptons. These are the leptons that, if a Z boson decay occurred, will have come from the Z boson.

In this next line of code, we will be creating two new variables that will store the array position. It might be useful to review arrays in C++. However, we will be assigning an impossible array position as a sort of check to test our code later.

Code Breakdown: Some things to keep in mind: you will need to define two new variables, one for the array position of the leading lepton and one for the array position of the sub-leading lepton. You will want to choose the correct variable type, so make sure to assign them the type that makes the most sense. And think of what type of number relates to an impossible array position.

Tasks: Write script that creates two new variables and assigns them impossible array positions.

7.3.4 Checkpoint

For this section, your macro should look similar to this, with the blanks filled in.

```
1 for ( long ... = "value", ...){  
2  
3     //Code for loading data for each event  
4  
5     //Code for retrieving number of leptons  
6  
7     //Code for requirement  
8  
9     //Code for array variables  
10 }
```

7.4 Macro Section 3: Identifying the Leading and Sub-leading Leptons

7.4.1 Initiating a Nested For Loop

As you recall from the ROOT/C++ guide, a nested for loop is simply a for loop within a for loop. In the previous section, we started a for loop to loop over all the events/collisions in our data files. Now that we are looping through every event in our data, we want to start a process to analyze each event that we loop through so we can identify the lepton with the highest transverse momentum (called the leading lepton) and the lepton with the second highest transverse

momentum (called the sub-leading lepton) within each event, and then store their information in separate TLorentzVectors. This will require a nested for loop.

To start, we will define a TLorentzVector for the leading lepton that we can store data in. We then need to create our for loop with its start, stop, and iteration conditions. Then, create a variable that represents the transverse momentum of the lepton we are looking at in the current event.

```
1 TLorentzVector "variable1";
2 for ("type" "variable2" = ...)
3 {
4     "type" "variable3" = (*lep_pt)[i];
5 }
```

Code Breakdown: In the code above, we first define our empty TLorentzVector that we will be storing data in. For the start, stop, and iteration conditions of the for loop, keep in mind what we are looping over in this for loop.

Further, the line of code with variable3 in it is simply assigning variable3 the value of the current lepton's (i) transverse momentum (lep_pt).

Next, we need to ensure that the lepton we are currently analyzing is indeed the leading lepton. Recall what it means for a lepton to be "leading" in order to fill in the condition for an if statement. You may need to use the property ".Pt()" of a TLorentzVector in order to fill in this condition.

Now that we know we have the leading lepton, we can then safely define variables for the rest of the lepton's (p_{\perp}, η, ϕ, E) information and store the current lepton's (p_{\perp}, η, ϕ, E) in these new variables.

To conclude this for loop, we need to set the information in the previously created TLorentzVector for the leading lepton to the information in the variables we just defined. You will need to use ".SetPtEtaPhiE()" on your TLorentzVector in order to do this. Finally, you need to set your previously defined array position variable for the leading lepton to the current leptons array position, effectively overwriting the impossible array position we set it to before.

Once this is done, it could be useful to run your macro and check to see if you are correctly identifying the lepton's positions. One way to know for sure is to check if the array variable being printed out is still the impossible number chosen earlier, or a new one that makes sense. To write a print statement, use this example:

```
1 std::cout << "Leading position is" << array variable name << std::endl;
```

Tasks:

- Create a nested for loop that identifies the leading lepton's array position and sets all of its components to a TLorentzVector.
- Do the same thing for the sub-leading lepton.

7.4.2 Checkpoint

For this section, your macro should look similar to this, with the blanks filled in. Note that you will need an additional condition for the sub-leading lepton's if statement in order to ensure that you don't just store the data of the leading lepton a second time.

```
1 TLorentzVector "variable1";
2 for ("type" "variable2" = ...)
3 {
4     "type" "variable3" = (*lep_pt)[i];
5     if("Condition that ensures leading lepton")
6     {
7         //Code for creating and storing lepton information
8
9         variable1.SetPtEtaPhiE("Variables for each lepton component
10        ")
11
12        //Code to set the current lepton's array position as the
13        leading lepton's array position
14    }
15 }
16 //Code for a for loop for the sub-leading lepton
```

7.4.3 Dilepton System

Once we have the $(p_{\perp}, \eta, \phi, E)$ stored for both the leading and sub-leading leptons, we will need to create another variable that allows us to store a two lepton (or dilepton) system with the leading and sub-leading leptons' Lorentz vectors. Recall that if a Z boson is present, it decays into the two highest momentum leptons in a collision, which is why we want to create a dilepton system.

Tasks:

- Create a new dilepton Lorentz vector variable.

7.5 Macro Section 4: Filling the Histogram

Now that you have created a dilepton system that stores the Lorentz vectors of both the leading and sub-leading leptons, think about what we actually want to plot in our histogram. Recall that our original goal is to find evidence for the existence of the Z boson by looking for high occurrence frequencies that are statistically significant. A great way to do this is by plotting masses of dilepton systems and seeing if their masses add up to the mass of the Z boson, 91 GeV.

Code Breakdown: To compute the mass of the dilepton system, you will need to use the ".M()" command on the dilepton system variable. It could also be beneficial to create a cout statement to print the masses of the dilepton systems.

Tasks:

- Compute the mass of the dilepton system.
- Fill the histogram.
- Draw the histogram.
- End the macro.

7.5.1 Checkpoint

Make sure to combine all your code from all sections to complete the macro.

7.6 Macro Section 5: Flavor, Charge, and Tight ID Requirements

Physics Context: Now that you should have a histogram with a very evident peak at roughly 91 GeV, we will look into several different methods to narrow down your result and make it more accurate. This will be useful for the next exercise. Recall that with Z boson decays, there are two requirements. The first is that the leptons that the Z boson decays into must be of the same flavor, such as two muons or two electrons. The second is that the leptons that the Z boson decays into must be of opposite charges, with one positive and one negative lepton.

There is also a third requirement that we can set on Z boson decays to ensure our data is only analyzing true Z boson decays. This requirement involves code essentially ensuring that the events your macro is looking at are detecting true leptons, and not other particles that ATLAS "thinks" are particles. You will need to ensure all three of these requirements are met to ensure that your macro is (for the most part) only analyzing events that are true $Z \rightarrow ll$ decays. The code for all these requirements should be written after the creation of your dilepton system and inside the first for loop.

7.6.1 Lepton Flavor

Since you will be setting a flavor requirement on the events the macro looks at, it would be a good idea to create a new histogram for the dilepton mass plot with the flavor requirement. Doing so for the other requirements (or combinations of requirements would also be a good idea). Doing this allows you to compare the plot with and without different requirements.

To figure out if two leptons are the same flavor, you will need to access the variable called "lep_type, which tells you the flavor of the leptons. This variable will have the flavor stored as an integer, with the same integers being same flavor leptons.

Code Breakdown: To do this, you will need to create a new pointer for the flavor, as well as set the branch address, just as you did in section 6.2. Think

about where you will want to code in this requirement. One thing to consider is you will only want to fill your flavor histogram **if** the flavor condition is met.

Tasks:

- Create a new histogram for the flavor requirement.
- Write script to fill this histogram with events that meet the flavor requirement.

7.6.2 Lepton Charge

Next, work towards applying the same process as above to a lepton charge requirement. The variable from the TTree you will want to access is the "lep_charge" variable.

Code Breakdown: Again, you will need to create a new pointer for the charge, as well as set the branch address. The lep_charge variable has a positive or negative 1 value, so think of a way to ensure your code only fills your charge histogram with oppositely charged leptons.

Tasks:

- Create a new histogram for the charge requirement.
- Write script to fill this histogram with events that meet the charge requirement.

7.6.3 Tight ID

Next, work towards applying the same process as above to a Tight ID requirement. This simply ensures the data being analyzed by the macro only includes leptons that are actually leptons, and not particles that are detected as leptons by ATLAS. The variable from the TTree you will want to access is the "lep_isTightID" variable.

Code Breakdown: You will need to create one last pointer for this requirement, as well as set the branch address. Keep in mind, however, that this variable is not an integer type, but rather a bool type, so its values take on either zero or one, meaning false or true, respectively. Remember, you will want the requirement to be true in order for a detected lepton to be a true lepton.

Tasks:

- Create a new histogram for the Tight ID requirement.
- Write script to fill this histogram with events that meet the Tight ID requirement.

7.6.4 Combining the Requirements

Tasks:

- Create another histogram that will plot the combination of all three requirements.
- Write script that fills this histogram only if **all** requirements are met.

8 Higgs Boson Exercise

8.1 A Quick Overview

In this exercise, you will use your ROOT and C++ knowledge, as well as your practice with the Z Boson exercise (this will be a big help) to write a macro that will create a histogram that provides evidence for the Higgs Boson's existence. This exercise will have less guidance, as much of the help you may need can be found or inferred from the previous exercise. You will work through the macro in sections, in which we will make sure it is clear what the code is doing and what the underlying physics is. These sections are:

- Macro, TChain, and Histogram Creation
- Loading the Data into the Macro
- Identifying the Four Leading Leptons
- Creating Different Lepton Combinations
- Flavor, Charge, and Tight ID Requirements
- Extra Requirements
- Ending the Macro

Some sections of this macro will be provided to you as fully understanding these lines of code is not important for the purposes of this exercise.

8.2 Macro Section 1: Macro, TChain, and Histogram Creation

For the completion of this section, refer back to Macro Section 1 of the Z Boson exercise. However, for this section, make sure to also create vectors for the three requirements, flavor, charge, and Tight ID, right off the bat.

Tasks:

- Create a voided macro
- Add all four data files to the TChain

- Create new vectors for the seven variables.
- Write script to tell the TChain where to find a vector's values and where to store these values
- Create a new histogram and TCanvas

8.2.1 Checkpoint

So far, your macro should look similar to this, with the blanks filled in.

```

1 #include <vector>
2 #include <iostream>
3 #include "TChain.h"
4 #include "TLorentzVector.h"
5
6 void HBoson() {
7
8 // Creating a TChain
9 TChain* chain = new TChain ("mini");
10
11 // Adding files to the TChain
12 chain->AddFile("DataA.root");
13 // Code for second file
14 // Code for third file
15 // Code for fourth file
16
17 // Creating Data Pointers/Vectors
18 vector<float>* lep_pt = new vector<float>;
19 // Code for second vector/coordinate
20 // Code for third vector/coordinate
21 // Code for fourth vector/coordinate
22 // Code for first requirement vector
23 // Code for second requirement vector
24 // Code for third requirement vector
25
26 // Storing the Data
27 chain->SetBranchAddress("lep_pt", & lep_pt);
28 // Code for storing the second variable
29 // Code for storing the third variable
30 // Code for storing the fourth variable
31 // Code for storing the first requirement variable
32 // Code for storing the second requirement variable
33 // Code for storing the third requirement variable
34
35 //Creating a Histogram
36 TCanvas *c1 = new TCanvas();
37
38 TH1F *h1 = new TH1F ("box-title", "plot-title; x-axis-title; y-axis
    -title",
39 number-of-bins, lower-x-boundary, upper-x-boundary);
40 }

```

8.3 Macro Section 2: Loading the Data into the Macro

Much of this section will be similar to Macro Section 2 from the previous exercise, except for the if statement that needs to be created and the array positioning.

8.3.1 If Statement Requirement

As was done in the previous exercise, some sort of requirement will need to be set so that the macro does not analyze any events that are not relevant to your search for the Higgs boson. Think about what type of events you want your macro to loop over. What does the Higgs boson decay into?

8.3.2 Array Positioning

Physics Context: As previously mentioned, the Higgs boson decays into four leptons. While none of the events the code is looking at should have less than four leptons, some may have more. Regardless of how many leptons are in an event, you will want to identify the four leading leptons, which are identified by their transverse momentum. These are the leptons that, if a Higgs boson decay occurred, will have come from the Higgs boson (or the two Z bosons the Higgs boson decays into first).

In this next line of code, you will be creating four new variables that will store the array position. It might be useful to review arrays in C++. However, you will be assigning an impossible array position as a sort of check to test your code later.

Tasks Write code that:

- Creates a for loop.
- Stores current entry in the previously defined long variable (found in the for loop).
- Retrieves the number of leptons in the current event.
- Skips over events that you do not want your macro to look at.
- Creates four new variables (one for each lepton momentum) and assign them impossible array positions.

8.3.3 Checkpoint

For this section, your macro should look similar to this, with the blanks filled in.

```

1 // Code to initiate for loop
2
3 // Code for loading data for each event
4
5 // Code for retrieving number of leptons
6
7 // Code for if statement requirement
8
9 // Code for four array variables
10 }

```

8.4 Macro Section 3: Identifying the Four Leading Leptons

8.4.1 Identifying the Leading Lepton's Components

You will need to create a nested for loop to loop over each lepton in the current event that the macro is on. Doing this will allow you to identify the four highest momentum leptons, which as previously mentioned, are the leptons that are most likely to have come from a Higgs boson decay.

Not only will you need to identify these leptons and their array positions, but you will also need to store their 4-vector components in a TLorentzVector to help with the next couple sections. The code required to do this is similar to that of the Z boson exercise, but there a few extra steps, and this time you aren't only trying to find the two leading leptons, but rather the four leading leptons, plus their TLorentzVector components. Use this partially filled code to do the above.

```

1 "Type" variable1;
2
3 for ("type" variable2 = ...){
4
5     "type" variable3 = (*lep_pt)[i];
6
7     if ( variable3 > variable1.Pt() ){
8
9         "type" variable4 = "value of current lepton's 2nd
10             TLorentzVector component"
11
12         // Code for assigning value of current lepton's 3rd
13         TLorentzVector component to a variable5
14
15         // Code for assigning value of current lepton's 4rth
16         TLorentzVector component to a variable6
17
18         variable1.SetPtEtaPhiE( variable3, variable4, variable5,
19             variable6 );
20
21         // Code for replacing array variable of the first lepton
22     }
23 }

```

Code Breakdown: The above code, which may seem confusing, is quite simple under closer observation. By creating `variable1`, your macro will automatically assign all four components to zero. Then, the code identifies the current lepton's momentum, and states "if the current lepton's momentum is higher than the `variable1` momentum value, then do ...". The code then identifies the current lepton's three other components, assigns it to `variable1`, and stores this leptons position. Next, the for loop does this all over again until it identifies a lepton whose momentum is larger than all the previous leptons the code has looped through, and stores this leptons four components and array position.

For `variable1`, think of what type is most appropriate to assign to this variable. Keep in mind this is the variable that will store the $(p_{\perp}, \eta, \phi, E)$ components of the highest momentum lepton.

Now that you have identified the current lepton's momentum, you will need to also identify the three other components of the current lepton. To do this, consider using pointers, as was used to store the value of the current lepton's momentum in `variable3`. This is all being done in the if statement as the if statement is meant to ensure you are only identifying the components of the highest momentum lepton in this event.

Once you have identified all four components for the highest lepton in this event, you will want to store them in `variable1` (think about what type of variable stores $(p_{\perp}, \eta, \phi, E)$) to assign `variable1` the correct type). Lastly, just as you did in section 7.3.1, you will want to write code that replaces the impossible array position previously assigned to the highest momentum lepton array position.

Tasks: Write code that identifies the leading lepton's four Lorentz vector components and its array position.

8.4.2 Identifying the Three Other Lepton's Components

Now that the highest momentum lepton's components and array position have been identified and stored, you will need to repeat the process for the three other leptons that come from a Higgs boson decay. The only modifications that will need to be made are creating some new variables as well as adding a second condition to the your if statement.

Code Breakdown: Your code will be very similar to the previous sections, but you will need to create a new variable for `variable1`, as this variable should store the $(p_{\perp}, \eta, \phi, E)$ components of the second highest momentum lepton. As for the if statement, you will want to ensure that this second nested for loop (and the third and fourth) do not simply store the leading momentum lepton's components and position. Think about what you can add to the if statement to ensure that the leading momentum lepton is being skipped over in your

code. You may need to use `&&`, which allows you to combine two if statements into one and `!=`, which means "does not equal". For the third and fourth highest momentum leptons, you may need to combine multiple if statements.

Tasks: Write code that identifies the second, third, and fourth highest momentum leptons 4-vector components and their respective array positions.

8.4.3 Section Tasks

Tasks: For the four highest momentum leptons in each event, write code that:

- Identifies all four of the given lepton's Lorentz vector components.
- Stores these components in an appropriate variable.
- Replaces each lepton's array position.

8.4.4 Checkpoint

For this section, your macro should look similar to this, with the blanks filled in.

```
1 "type" variable1;
2
3 for ("type" variable2 = ... ){
4
5     "type" variable3 = (*lep_pt)[i];
6
7     if ( variable3 > variable1.Pt() ){
8
9         "type" variable4 = "value of current lepton's 2nd component
10
11         // Code for storing current lepton's 3rd component in
12         variable5
13
14         // Code for storing current lepton's 4th component in
15         variable6
16
17         variable1.SetPtEtaPhiE(variable2, variable4, variable5,
18         variable6);
19
20         // Code for replacing array variable of the highest
21         momentum lepton
22     }
23 }
24
25 // Nested for loop for identifying second highest momentum lepton
26 // position and components
27
28 // Nested for loop for identifying third highest momentum lepton
29 // position and components
30
31 // Nested for loop for identifying fourth highest momentum lepton
32 // position and components
```

8.5 Macro Section 4: Creating Different Lepton Combinations

Now that you have identified the positions and components of the four highest momentum leptons, you will now need to work towards figuring out which unique combinations of these leptons came from a Higgs boson decay. For instance, lepton 1 and lepton 3 could have decayed from Z boson 1, and lepton 2 and 4 could have decayed from Z boson 2. Naturally, there are 6 combinations of possible lepton pairings. So, you will need to create new variables that represent the 6 different combinations of possible Z boson pairings. You will also need to create a new variable for the 4-lepton system, which will be used later.

Code Breakdown: When creating these new variables (6 new variables for the 6 possible dilepton pairings and one for the 4-lepton system), consider what type is best to assign to these variables. You will be summing different combinations of the variables that store the components of each of the leptons earlier identified.

Tasks: Write code that:

- Creates 6 new dilepton system variables, one for each unique combination.
- Creates a 4-lepton system.

8.6 Macro Section 5: Flavor, Charge, and Tight ID Requirements

For this section, you will be applying the flavor, charge, and Tight ID requirements to the data to further narrow down what the macro is analyzing. Simultaneously, you will create a list of possible candidates for dilepton systems that came from a Higgs boson decay.

8.6.1 Creating Requirement Variables

Tasks: Create variables that store the flavor, charge, and Tight ID value for each of the four leptons.

8.6.2 Creating the Pairings List

For this section, rather than guiding you along, we will provide the needed code for you. Make sure you understand what is going on in the code before moving on. The code below will create a list of all possible pairings of two dilepton systems.

```
1 vector< pair<TLorentzVector, TLorentzVector> > candidates;  
2 candidates.reserve(6);
```

Code Breakdown: In the first line of code, a new vector variable is being created. This vector is coded in such a way that it stores a pair of TLorentzVectors, meant to be the pair of dilepton systems created earlier. It also creates a list called "candidates".

The second line of code simply reserves, or creates, 6 blank entries in the candidates list in which different dilepton pairings can be stored.

8.6.3 Appending to the Candidates List

Physics Context: As previously mentioned, bosons, such as the Z boson, can only decay into leptons that are of the same flavor (two electrons or two muons) and leptons that are oppositely charged. As discussed, the Tight ID requirement is simply to ensure that a lepton detection is in fact a lepton and not a particle causing detectors to mistake it for a lepton. While these requirements are true for a boson decaying into two leptons, they are not fully accurate for a Higgs boson decaying into four leptons, as it first decays into two Z bosons, then four leptons. This means that a Higgs can decay into two muons and two electrons, with the pairs each coming from the same Z boson (as the Z boson cannot violate the flavor requirement).

Next, you should have everything set up to allow you to start adding candidates to the list. However, you will want to only add candidates that follow the flavor, charge, and Tight ID requirements, as this will increase the likelihood that candidates in the list are dilepton systems that came from a Higgs boson decay.

To do this, you will need to create an if statement with multiple conditions in it. These conditions need to ensure that the candidates that are being added to the candidates list are all likely Higgs decay products. Here is an example to follow.

```
1 if ("all requirements are met"){
2
3     candidates.push_back ( make_pair (dilepton1, dilepton2) );
4 }
```

Code Breakdown: Within the if statement, you should have multiple conditions that need to be met before a candidate is "pushed back", or added, to the candidates list. When choosing which dilepton system to make a pair, make sure to note which leptons are paired, as this will help you write your if statement conditions. For example, if your first pair is with leptons 1 and 2, and leptons 3 and 4, you will want to make sure that leptons 1 and 2 meet the flavor, charge, and Tight ID requirements, and that leptons 3 and 4 do the same. Note how leptons 1 and 3 do not have to meet the flavor and charge requirements as, in this line of code, they are not paired up within the same dilepton system. You will need to repeat this process for the five other possible combinations.

Tasks: Create 6 different if statements that append the 6 possible 4-lepton combinations.

8.6.4 Sorting the Candidates

Once you have appended the candidates to the list, you will need to sort the dilepton pairs by their invariant masses. The code will be provided for you, but make sure you understand how this works before moving on.

```
1 sort( candidates.begin() , candidates.end() ,
2       []( pair<TLorentzVector , TLorentzVector> a ,
3           pair<TLorentzVector , TLorentzVector> b )
4       { return (a.first.M() > b.first.M())
5           || (a.first.M()==b.first.M()
6             && a.second.M() > b.second.M()); } );
```

Code Breakdown: The code first creates two pairs of dilepton systems, each with two TLorentzVectors. The first pair is labelled a, and the second b. The rest of the code sorts the candidates by returning a candidate if the first dilepton's system first lepton's invariant mass is greater than that of the second dilepton system. If they are equal, the code then resorts to sorting based off the second lepton's invariant mass in each dilepton pair.

8.6.5 Filling the Histogram

To conclude this section, you will need to take the candidates that meet the three requirements and fill your histogram with their masses. However, because of the way C++ works, you need to write in code that ensures the macro will not crash. To do this, an if statement that requires the candidates list to not be empty, as it is possible that none of the candidates meet the criteria, needs to be written.

```
1 if ( ... ){
2
3     "type" variable1 = candidates.front().first + ...
4
5     // Fill histogram
6 }
```

Code Breakdown: For the if statement, you will need to use ".empty()" on the candidates list to check if the list is empty, and recall the desired condition is to only fill the histogram if the candidates list being empty is false. Next, you will need to create a variable1 that stores the 4-vector components of the highest invariant mass candidate's first and second pair (dilepton system). The front function ensures you are storing the first candidate's information, and the first function ensures you are storing the first pair's information. To complete the code, do the same for the second pair of the first candidate.

To fill the histogram, consider what it is you actually want to plot. Think back to the Z boson exercise and what you plotted there (and how you coded this).

8.6.6 Checkpoint

For this section, your macro should similar to this, with the blanks filled in.

```
1 // Code for first lepton's flavor
2 // Code for second lepton's flavor
3 // Code for third lepton's flavor
4 // Code for fourth lepton's flavor
5
6 // Code for first lepton's charge
7 // Code for second lepton's charge
8 // Code for third lepton's charge
9 // Code for fourth lepton's charge
10
11 // Code for first lepton's Tight ID value
12 // Code for second lepton's Tight ID value
13 // Code for third lepton's Tight ID value
14 // Code for fourth lepton's Tight ID value
15
16 vector< pair<TLorentzVector, TLorentzVector> > candidates;
17 candidates.reserve(6);
18
19 if ("all requirements are met"){
20     candidates.pushback (make_pair ("dilepton1", "dilepton2") );
21 }
22
23 // Code for second combination
24 // Code for third combination
25 // Code for fourth combination
26 // Code for fifth combination
27 // Code for sixth combination
28
29 sort( candidates.begin() , candidates.end() ,
30     []( pair<TLorentzVector, TLorentzVector> a ,
31     pair<TLorentzVector, TLorentzVector> b )
32     { return (a.first.M() > b.first.M())
33     || (a.first.M()==b.first.M()
34     && a.second.M() > b.second.M()); } );
35
36 if (...){
37     "type" variable1 = candidates.front().first + ...
38     // Code to fill the histogram
39 }
```

8.7 Macro Section 6: Ending the Macro

To end the macro, make sure you draw the histogram and print the TCanvas after combining your code from all the sections above.

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References

- [1] Review of the 13 TeV ATLAS Open Data release. Technical report, CERN, Geneva, 2020. All figures including auxiliary figures are available at <https://atlas.web.cern.ch/Atlas/GROUPS/PHYSICS/PUBNOTES/ATL-OREACH-PUB-2020-001>.
- [2] ATLAS Collaboration. ATLAS 13 TeV samples collection exactly two leptons (electron or muon), for 2020 open data release, 2020.
- [3] ATLAS Collaboration. The ATLAS Experiment at the CERN Large Hadron Collider. *JINST*, 3:S08003, 2008. Also published by CERN Geneva in 2010.
- [4] ATLAS Collaboration. ATLAS Standard Model. General Photo, 2021.
- [5] ATLAS Collaboration. A detailed map of Higgs boson interactions by the ATLAS experiment ten years after the discovery. *Nature*, 607:52–59, 2022.